

**SEMIKARBAZID ASOSIDAGI YANGI KOMPLEKS BIRIKMALARNING
BIOLOGIK FAOLLIGI VA O‘TKIR ZAXARLIGI IN SILICO TAXLILI**

Tajieva Galiya Ruslanovna

Ibragimova Mavlyuda Ruzmetovna

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Fanlar Akademiyasi

Umumiy va noorganik kimyo instituti

Toshkent, O‘zbekiston

smart_girl.7@mail.ru, +99893 0926556

Annotatsiya: *Semikarbazid va salitsil anhidrididan olingan yangi semikarbazid hosilalarini taxmin qilingan biologik faollik va o‘tkir zaharligini in silico usuli yordamida o‘rganildi hamda baholandi. Tadqiqotga ko‘ra, o‘rganilayotgan komplekslar keng ko‘lamli bioaktivlikni namoyish qilish potentsialiga yega va past zaharlidir, bu komplekslar nojo‘ya ta’sirlarni keltirib chiqarish yehtimoli past yekanligini ko‘rsatadi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *semikarbazid, semikarbazonlar, in silico, fitopatogenlar, biologik faollik, o‘tkir toksiklik.*

**IN SILICO ПРОГНОЗ БИОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ И ОСТРОЙ
ТОКСИЧНОСТИ НОВЫХ КОМПЛЕКСНЫХ СОЕДИНЕНИЙ НА
ОСНОВЕ СЕМИКАРБАЗИДА**

Аннотация: *Исследование новых производных семикарбазида, полученных на основе семикарбазида и салицилового ангидрида, методом in silico для консенсусной оценки прогнозируемой биологической активности и острой токсичности. Согласно исследованию изучаемые комплексы могут, обладают потенциалом для проявления широкого спектра биоактивности, являются малотоксичными, что говорит о том, что комплексы имеют низкую вероятность вызывать нежелательные побочные эффекты.*

Ключевые слова: *семикарбазид, семикарбазоны, in silico, фитопатогены, биологическая активность, острая токсичность.*

**IN SILICO PREDICTION OF BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY AND ACUTE
TOXICITY OF NEW COMPLEX COMPOUNDS BASED ON
SEMICARBAZIDE.**

Annotation: *In silico examination of new semicarbazide derivatives, which are derived from semicarbazide and salicylic anhydride, for establishing a unified evaluation of the anticipated biological activities and acute toxicity has been carried out. The study discloses that the complexes studied demonstrate potential across a wide variety of bioactivities, with low toxicity levels, indicating that the complexes have a low probability of causing undesirable side effects.*

Key words: semicarbazide, semicarbazones, *in silico*, phytopathogens, biological activity, acute toxicity.

New semicarbazide derivatives, semicarbazones, were chosen for *in silico* research. The semicarbazones were synthesized by using semicarbazide and salicylic anhydride. There is evidence in the literature that semicarbazones have biological activity and are used as plant growth regulators, which can increase productivity [1].

The physicochemical studies yielded findings on the composition and structure of novel compounds, specifically mixed-ligand complexes $C_8H_{10}N_4OCo$ and $C_8H_9N_3O_2$.

Computer modelling techniques called *in silico* are widely used to fully evaluate new compounds. The *in silico* approach permits researchers to model different features and interactions of molecules, biochemical processes, and physiological systems based solely on the compound's structure. *In silico* toxicity prediction is a valuable aid that complements existing *in vitro* techniques for determining the adverse effects of chemicals. This approach minimises the duration it takes to carry out physical experiments and the resultant expenses. Consequently, a substance's potential toxicity can be assessed, which decreases the necessity for expensive, time-consuming testing. Furthermore, computer modelling enables researchers to examine the behaviour of diverse molecules and envisage their efficacy in biological systems, thus paving the way for the design of improved and harmless fertilisers. Thus, the use of *in silico* computer modeling methods is an important tool for the study of bioactive substances and the development of new drugs.

The selected programs for the research were PASS (Prediction of Activity Spectra for Substances) [2] and GUSAR (General Unrestricted Structure-Activity Relationships) [3], which are highly probable.

Table I

Results of predicting the biological effects of semicarbazide complex compounds

Name	Confidence	
	$C_8H_{10}N_4OCo$	$C_8H_9N_3O_2$
Actinomyces sp.	0.0099	
Bacillus	0.1256	0.1033
Burkholderia	0.1750	0.1753
Chromobacterium	0.0320	
Clostridium	0.0409	
Corynebacterium jeikeium	0.0181	
Mycobacterium marinum	0.2444	0.2186
Mycoplasma gallisepticum	0.0121	
Pectobacterium atrosepticum	0.0381	

For the investigated compounds, the predictive model reveals activity that is evident in their capacity to limit the growth of a specific set of plant pathogenic

bacteria, ranging from 0.0099 to 0.2444. Refer to Table 1 for the corresponding calculations.

Species such as Clostridium primarily cause bacteriosis in flax, while Corynebacterium causes wilting and bacterial canker in tomatoes. Non-motile phytopathogenic bacteria, including Actinomyces and Mycobacterium, can cause various plant diseases [4,5]. Nevertheless, as shown in Table 1, the metal complex has demonstrated higher biological activity against a greater range of phytopathogens. The forecast indicates no detection of fungicidal activity in the announced complexes. Their capability to hinder the growth of phytopathogenic bacteria may facilitate the advancement of novel methods for biological control of plant ailments.

Table II

Results of prediction of toxic effects of ligand C₈H₉N₃O₂

Rat acute toxicity predicted by GUSAR

Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)	Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)
0,339 in AD	0,014 in AD	0,939 in AD	0,828 in AD

Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)
364,700 in AD	172,700 in AD	1454,000 in AD	1125,000 in AD

Acute Rodent Toxicity Classification of Chemicals by OECD Project

Rat IP LD50 Classification	Rat IV LD50 Classification	Rat Oral LD50 Classification	Rat SC LD50 Classification
Class 4 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 5 in AD

The GUSAR web server's toxicity prediction results reveal that compound C₈H₉N₃O₂ is classified under toxicity classes IV and V. The substance C₈H₁₀N₄OC_o belongs to toxicity class 5, in accordance with data on the classification of chemical substances for acute toxicity for rodents based on the OECD project "Rat SC LD50 Classification". The preliminary forecast indicates that the tested compound does not have a significant toxic effect.

Table III

Results of prediction of toxic effects of the complex $C_8H_{10}N_4OCo$.

Rat acute toxicity predicted by GUSAR			
Rat IP LD50 Log10(mmol/kg)	Rat IV LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 log10(mmol/kg)	Rat SC LD50 log10(mmol/kg)
0,165 in AD	-0,191 in AD	0,314 in AD	0,188 in AD
Rat IP LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat IV LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat Oral LD50 (mg/kg)	Rat SC LD50 (mg/kg)
344,000 in AD	151,400 in AD	484,600 in AD	362,500 in AD
Acute Rodent Toxicity Classification of Chemicals by OECD Project			
Rat IP LD50 Classification	Rat IV LD50 Classification	Rat Oral LD50 Classification	Rat SC LD50 Classification
Class 4 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 4 in AD	Class 4 in AD

Based on the results of the toxicity prediction (Table 3), the compound $C_8H_{10}N_4OCo$ is classified as belonging to toxicity class IV according to the consensus LD50 indicator. Therefore, the analyzed structure is considered to have low toxicity.

The ability to hinder the proliferation of phytopathogenic bacteria has the potential to enhance disease resistance or facilitate the creation of novel plant protection approaches. In totality, these latest compounds foster a hopeful research domain, as their plausible utilities hold promise to provide significant agricultural gains. Further research is necessary through in vitro and in vivo studies to ascertain and validate the activity types of biologically active substances identified through in silico methods, leading to the development of drugs.

REFERENCES:

1. Bove Stiven, Rademaxer Vilgelm, Nyusom Larri Dj., Fergyuson Gregori P. Application of a growth regulator based on semicarbazone to increase yield. Pat. 004532 US.2004
2. Filimonov D.A., Lagunin A.A., Glorizova T.A. Prediction of the biological activity spectra of organic compounds using the PASS online web resource // - Chem Heterocycl. - 2014. - Comp 3., P. 444 - 45.
3. Lagunin, A. QSAR modelling of rat acute toxicity on the basis of PASS prediction / A. Lagunin, A. Zakharov, D. Filimonov, V. Poroikov. – Text (visual) : unmediated // Mol. Inform. – 2011., Vol. 30., P. 241 – 250
4. Gorlenko M.V. Bakterialnye bolezni rastenij//Izd.vysshaya shkola. Moskva. 1996. S. 29, 234-236
5. Vasilev D.A., Sherbakov A.A. Metody obshej bakteriologii // Ulyanovsk, 2003.
6. Ochilovich, S. Z., & Sadirovich, S. N. (2022, May). KINEMATIC STUDY OF FLAT BASE MECHANISMS. In *E Conference Zone* (pp. 61-69).